
Role of Educational Institute in promoting and preserving the language in Arunachal Pradesh under NEP 1968

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ABSTRACT

Education plays a very important role in preserving and promoting language. It helps us to understand the value of language when it is being used in classroom teaching as the medium of instruction. Arunachal Pradesh is a state without any link language among the tribes of the state. The influence of Hindi as a medium of communication in daily use and English as official language among the different tribes has decreased the numbers of active indigenous speakers.

Education in its general sense is a form of learning in which knowledge: skills, values and beliefs are transfer from the learned members of the society to young learners of the society. Education plays an acculturating role. It refines sensitivities and perceptions that contribute to national solidity, a scientific temper and independence of mind and spirit. Education develops man power for different levels of the economy. It is also the substrate on which research and development flourish, being the ultimate guarantee of national self reliance. Education is a unique investment in the present and the future. In today's global world, the battle for the preservation of the indigenous language deals not only with the use of language in social domains but also the use of the language in the education and academic institutions.

Education plays a significant role in the transfer of the languages it is evident from the introduction of Assamese during 1950s and Hindi in 1970s as the second language in the class room teachings. This increases the numbers of speakers of both languages in Arunachal Pradesh. Use of a language other than a mother tongue in schools is common place in Arunachal leading the students to use more prestige

language and transferring it from classroom to different domains of language use. It is due to the influence of globalization, that foreign tongue, particularly Hindi and English are encouraged among the students to learn and use. These Languages are considered as a key towards the expanded opportunities of the global economy. Members of already marginalized groups face greater challenges not only to succeeding in school but also in understanding enrollment procedures and communicating with educational officials. The numbers of drop outs among the rural students is one of the prime examples that are quite common in the Galo community due to less understanding of the language use in teaching and learning. Teaching in mother tongues makes education more accessible and gives native speakers an equal chance to get succeed in their class. Research in the fields of education, linguistics, anthropology and cognitive psychology is unequivocal on one point: students who enter school with a primary language other than the national or dominant language perform significantly better on academic tasks when they receive consistent and cumulative academic support in the native/heritage language (McCarty, 2003). The numbers of school implementing the courses of native language also plays a significant role in numbers of competent speakers in the community.

National Educational Policy 1968- Three Language formula in Promotion of the Languages

The National policy of 1968 marked a significant step in the history of education in post-independence india. It aimed to promote national progress, a sense of common citizenship and culture, and to strengthen national integration. It laid stress on the need for an essential reconstruction of the education system, to improve its quality at all stages, and gave much greater attention to science and technology, the cultivation of moral values and a closer relation between education and the life of the people. Since the adoption of the 1968 policy, there has been considerable expansion in educational facilities all over the country at all levels. Perhaps the most notable development has been the acceptance of a common structure of education throughout the country and the introduction of the 10+2+3 system by most states. “The Concept of a national system of Education implies that, up to a given level, all students, irrespective of caste, creed, location or sex, have access to education of a comparable quality”. The national policy of Education also stress on the use of the language as the medium of instruction in schools, colleges and universities. It has been spelt out in the National policy on Education (NPE’86) that, “mother tongue has organic connection with thought: hence the best means in developing cognitive abilities in the children is education through their mother tongue”. The NPE’86 has directs all the states in the country to create space for children’s language in their schools at least at the primary school level when children are still at the formative stage. It has played a significant role in the understanding of the various languages.

India speaks and learns in many languages from North to South and West to East. So the policy of National Education in imparting knowledge and information in class room plays a significant role in the stability of the language. In order to understand the multi language of India and also to protect and preserve the minority language in India. The National policy of Education introduces three languages formula for the stability of the minority languages with the major language like Hindi. As India is a multi lingual nation a person has to be acquainted with different languages and speaks in those languages. A student who has learnt only his/her mother tongue cannot acquire knowledge regarding the other regions and languages unless it is translated into his/her language. This formula (TFL) which emerged as a political consensus on languages in school education was a strategy (not a policy) to accommodate at least three languages within the ten years of schooling” (Pattanayak, D.P.1986). The All India council for education recommended the adoption of the three language formula in Sept. 1956 (Mallikarjun, 2002). According to this formula, every child has to learn the following:

1. The mother tongue or the regional language;
2. The official language of the union or the associate official language of the union so long as it exists (official Language of the Union is Hindi and its associate official language is Englis);
3. Modern Indian Language or a foreign language, not covered under (1) & (2) above and other than that used as the medium of instruction.

1 The First Language (L1)

The Language that we learn from our childhood is usually spoken b our parents, family members and the other people around us. This is known as our first language or L1. Since this is the language we know best and use commonly, the government decided that the medium of instruction at primary stage should be one’s own regional language. First language is acquired naturally, through interacting with family members and friends without much formal instruction. But even though, we may communicate effectively in our first language, many of us do not have a complete knowledge of all the sounds an letters of the language or its grammar. This is because we acquire it informally. Therefore formal instruction in thr first language is provided in the school.

2. The Second Language (L2):

Education aims to expose the learner to various situations and develop such ability which enables him/her to gain knowledge from every possible source and share the same with others. Therefore, the learner needs to learn the second language (L2)

Which in our country usually is either Hindi or English. The Second language is learn consciously and deliberately for a specific purpose i.e., to gather information and acquire knowledge. The sounds, letters and grammar of the second language can be learn properly only when they are deliberately taught by the teachers and consciously learn by the students. Under the three language formula, Second language (L2) is taught at a later stage in the primary school curriculum, after the child has already taught one language well i.e. his/her (L1). We use first language to communicate and to express our feelings and thoughts in our day to day life situations. On the other hand, second language is used in situation other than personnel.

3. The Third Language (L3)

Third Language plays an importance role in a multi lingual society. This is an additional language that you learn for your uses in an international community where both your first language and second language may not work there. Such as if a person first language is Galo and second language is Hindi. She/he may not be able to communicate in an area where the language is Portuguese. In order to understand Portuguese if you study that language as a subject in schools, that becomes as third language.

Thus the three languages formula led the children to learn different languages in the formal study in academic institutions. The underline merit of this formula in the promotion of multilingualism is hardly questionable and best represents the multilingual character of the nation' (Kachru 1997; Krishnamurt 1998). But this formula has been observed more in the breach than in the observance. It is found that numbers of states follow two languages formula such as the Hindi speaking states of India studies only Hindi and English in their schools while the southern parts of the states focus more in English and their mother tongue ignoring the learning o other languages.

In case of Arunachal Pradesh under 1968, the school focuses more in Hindi and English teaching ignoring completely mother tongue. Most of the schools do not give any importance in the teaching of any indigenous language. This has led to the adverse effect in indigenous languages of the tribe in the state. The students are restricted to use their mother tongue in class room communication leading to the growth of incompetent language speakers in the community finally resulting in language shift of many students towards dominant language. This leads to reducing of the numbers of active speakers in a tribe.

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